

EXACT QUASI-CLASSICAL ASYMPTOTIC BEYOND MASLOV CANONICAL OPERATOR AND QUANTUM JUMPS NATURE

J. Foukzon¹, A.A.Potapov², S.A. Podosenov³

¹Israel Institute of Technology.

²IRE RAS,

³All-Russian Scientific-Research Institute

Abstract:

Exact quasi-classical asymptotic beyond WKB-theory and beyond Maslov canonical operator to the Colombeau solutions of the n -dimensional Schrödinger equation is presented. Quantum jumps nature is considered successfully. We pointed out that an explanation of quantum jumps can be found to result from Colombeau solutions of the Schrödinger equation alone without additional postulates.

Keywords:

Quantum jumps, quantum measurements theory, quantum averages, limiting quantum trajectory, Schrödinger equation, Stochastic quantum jump equation, Colombeau solution, Feynman path integral, Maslov canonical operator, Feynman-Colombeau propagator.

1. Introduction

A number of experiments on trapped single ions or atoms have been performed in recent years [1,2,3,4]. Monitoring the intensity of scattered laser light off of such systems has shown abrupt changes that have been cited as evidence of "quantum jumps" between states of the scattered ion or atom. The existence of such jumps was required by Bohr in his theory of the atom. Bohr's quantum jumps between atomic states [5] were the first form of quantum dynamics to be postulated. He assumed that an atom remained in an atomic eigen state until it made an instantaneous jump to another state with the emission or absorption of a photon. Since these jumps do not appear to occur in solutions of the Schrödinger equation, something similar to Bohr's idea has been added as an extra postulate in modern quantum mechanics.

Stochastic quantum jump equations [6], [7],[8] were introduced as a tool for simulating the dynamics of a dissipative system with a large Hilbert space and their links with quantum measurement theory were also noted [9],[10],[11],[12],[13]. This measurement interpretation is generally known as quantum trajectory theory [14]. By adding filter cavities as part of the apparatus, even the quantum jumps in the dressed state model can be interpreted as approximations to measurement-induced jumps [15].

The question arises whether an explanation of these jumps can be found to result from an Colombeau solution [16]-[18] $(\Psi_\varepsilon(x, t; \hbar))_\varepsilon$ of the Schrödinger equation alone without additional postulates. We found exact quasi-classical asymptotic of the quantum averages with position variable with localized initial data.

$$(\langle i, t, x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon \rangle)_\varepsilon = \left(\int x_i |\Psi_\varepsilon(x, t, x_0; \hbar)|^2 dx \right)_\varepsilon, \varepsilon \in (0, 1], x, x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^d, i = 1, \dots, d, \quad (1.1)$$

i.e. we found the limiting Colombeau quantum averages (limiting Colombeau quantum trajectories) such that[18]:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\langle i, t, x_0; \varepsilon \rangle)_\varepsilon = \left(\lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \langle i, t, x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon \rangle \right)_\varepsilon = \\ & = \left(\lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int x_i |\Psi_\varepsilon(x, t, x_0; \hbar)|^2 dx \right)_\varepsilon, \varepsilon \in (0, 1], x \in \mathbb{R}^d, i = 1, \dots, d, t \in [0, T] \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

And limiting quantum trajectories $\mathbf{q}(t, x_0) = \{q_1(t, x_0), \dots, q_d(t, x_0)\} \in \mathbb{R}^d, t \in [0, T]$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} q_i(t, x_0) & = \langle i, t, x_0 \rangle = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \langle i, t, x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon \rangle = \\ & = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int x_i |\Psi_\varepsilon(x, t, x_0; \hbar)|^2 dx, x \in \mathbb{R}^d, i = 1, \dots, d \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

if limit in LHS of Eq.(1.3) exist.

The physical interpretation of these asymptotic given below, shows that the answer is "yes" for the limiting quantum trajectories with localized initial data.

Note that an axiom of quantum measurement is: if the particle is in some state $|\Psi_{t,\varepsilon}\rangle$ that the probability $P(x, \delta x)$ of getting a result $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$ at instant t with an accuracy of $\|\delta x\| \ll 1$ will be given by

$$P_t(x, \delta x, x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon) = \int_{\|x-x'\| \leq \|\delta x\|} |\langle x' | \Psi_{t,\varepsilon} \rangle|^2 dx' = \int_{\|x-x'\| \leq \|\delta x\|} |\Psi_\varepsilon(x', t, x_0; \hbar)|^2 dx'. \quad (1.4)$$

We rewrite now Eq.(1.4) of the form

$$P_t(x, \delta x, x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{d/2} \|\delta x\|^d} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} |\Psi_\varepsilon(x', t, x_0; \hbar)|^2 \exp \left[-\frac{\|x-x'\|^2}{\|\delta x\|^2} \right] dx'. \quad (1.5)$$

We define well ocalized limiting quantum trajectories

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{q}(t) & = \mathbf{q}(t, x_0) = \{q_1(t, x_0), \dots, q_d(t, x_0)\} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \\ \mathbf{q}(0, x_0) & = x_0, t \in [0, T] \end{aligned} \text{ such that:}$$

$$\left(\lim_{\|\delta \mathbf{q}(t)\| \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} P_t(\mathbf{q}(t), \delta \mathbf{q}(t), x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon) \right)_\varepsilon = 1 \quad (1.6)$$

And well localized limiting quantum trajectories $\mathbf{q}(t) = \mathbf{q}(t, x_0) = \{q_1(t, x_0), \dots, q_d(t, x_0)\} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \mathbf{q}(0, x_0) = x_0, t \in [0, T]$ such that:

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\|\delta \mathbf{q}(t)\| \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} P_t(\mathbf{q}(t), \delta \mathbf{q}(t), x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon) = 1 \quad (1.7)$$

if limit in LHS of Eq.(1.7) exist.

2. Colombeau solutions of the Schrödinger equation and corresponding path integral representation

Let $\mathbf{H}$ be a complex infinite dimensional separable Hilbert space, with inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and norm $|\cdot|$.

Let us consider Schrödinger equation:

$$-i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial \Psi(t)}{\partial t} \right) + \hat{H}(t)\Psi(t) = 0, \Psi(0) = \Psi_0(x), (2.1)$$

$$H(t) = -\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \Delta + V(x, t). (2.2)$$

Here operator $H(t): \mathbb{R} \times \mathbf{H} \rightarrow \mathbf{H}$ is essentially self-adjoint, $\hat{H}(t)$ is the closure of $H(t)$.

Theorem 2.1. [19],[20]. Assume that: (1) $\Psi_0(x) \in L_2(\mathbb{R}^d)$, (2) $V(x, t)$ is continuous and $\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d, t \in [0, T]} |V(x, t)| < +\infty$. Then corresponding solution of the Schrödinger equation (2.1)-(2.2)

exist and can be represented via formulae

$$\Psi(t, x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{nm}{4\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d(n+1)/2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \dots \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} dx_0 dx_1 \dots dx_n \Psi_0(x_0) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}; t) \right], (2.3)$$

where we have set $x_{n+1} = x$ and

$$S(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}; t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{m}{4} \frac{|x_{i+1} - x_i|^2}{(t/n)^2} - V(x_{i+1}, t_i) \right], (2.4)$$

where $t_i = \frac{it}{n}$. Let $q_n(t)$ be a trajectory; that is, a function from $[0, t]$ to $\mathbb{R}^d$ with $q_n(0) = x_0$ and set $q_n(t_i) = x_i, i = 1, \dots, n + 1$. We rewrite Eq.(2.3) for a future application symbolically for short of the following form

$$\Psi(t, x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{q_n(t)=x} D[q_n(t)] \Psi_0(q_n(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S(q_n(t), x; t) \right], (2.5)$$

where we have set (i) $S(q_n(t), x; t) = S(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}; t)$ and (ii) $D[q_n(t)]$ that is, a

$$D[q_n(t)] = \left(\frac{nm}{4\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d(n+1)/2} \prod_{j=0}^n dx_j. (2.6)$$

Trotter and Kato well known classical results give a precise meaning to the Feynman integral when the potential $V(x, t)$ is sufficiently regular [18]-[19]. However if potential $V(x, t)$ is a non-regular this is well known problem to represent solution of the Schrödinger equation (2.1)-(2.2) via formulae (2.3), see [19].

We avoided this difficulty using contemporary Colombeau framework [16]-[18]. Using replacement $x_i \rightarrow \frac{x_i}{1 + \varepsilon^{2k} |x_i|^{2k}}, \varepsilon \in (0, 1], k \geq 1$ we obtain from potential $V(x, t)$ regularized potential $V_\varepsilon(x, t), \varepsilon \in (0, 1]$, such that $V_{\varepsilon=0}(x, t) = V(x, t)$ and

- (i) $(V_\varepsilon(x, t))_\varepsilon \in G(\mathbb{R}^d)$,
- (ii) $\sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^d, t \in [0, T]} |V_\varepsilon(x, t)| < +\infty, \varepsilon \in (0, 1]. (2.7)$

Here $G(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is Colombeau algebra of Colombeau generalized functions [16]-[18].

Finally we obtain regularized Schrödinger equation of Colombeau form [16]-[18]:

$$-i\hbar \left(\frac{\partial \Psi_\varepsilon(t)}{\partial t} \right)_\varepsilon + \left(\hat{H}_\varepsilon(t) \Psi_\varepsilon(t) \right)_\varepsilon = 0, \quad (\Psi_\varepsilon(0))_\varepsilon = \Psi_0(x), \quad (2.8)$$

$$H_\varepsilon(t) = -\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \Delta + V_\varepsilon(x, t). \quad (2.9)$$

Using the inequality (2.7) Theorem 2.1 asserts again that corresponding solution of the Schrödinger equation (2.8)-(2.9) exist and can be represented via formulae [18]:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \\ & \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{nm}{4\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d(n+1)/2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \dots \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} dx_0 dx_1 \dots dx_n \Psi_0(x_0) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}; t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where we have set $x_{n+1} = x$ and

$$S_\varepsilon(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}; t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{m}{4} \frac{|x_{i+1} - x_i|^2}{(t/n)^2} - V_\varepsilon(x_{i+1}, t_i) \right], \quad (2.11)$$

where we have set $t_i = \frac{it}{n}$.

We rewrite Eq.(2.10) for a future application symbolically of the following form

$$(\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{q_n(t)=x} D[q_n(t)] \Psi_0(q_n(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(q_n(t); t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon, \quad (2.12)$$

Or of the following form

$$(\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Psi_{\varepsilon, n}(t, x) \right)_\varepsilon = \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{q(t)=x} D_n[q(t)] \Psi_0(q_n(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t); t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon. \quad (2.13)$$

For the limit in RHS of (2.12) and (2.13) we will be used canonical path integral notation

$$(\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \left(\int_{q(t)=x} D[q(t)] \Psi_0(q(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t)) \right] \right)_\varepsilon, \quad (2.14)$$

where $S_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t)) = \int_0^t \left[\frac{m}{4} \dot{q}^2(s) - V_\varepsilon(q(s), s) \right] ds$.

Substitution $n = 8k + 7$ into RHS of the Eq.(2.10) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & (\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \\ & \left(\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{(8k+7)m}{4\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d(4k+4)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \dots \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} dx_0 dx_1 \dots dx_{8k+7} \Psi_0(x_0) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{8k+7}, x_{8k+8}; t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

We rewrite Eq.(2.15) for a future application symbolically of the following form

$$(\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{q_n(t)=x} D^+[q_n(t)] \Psi_0(q_n(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(q_n(t); t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon, \quad (2.16)$$

or of the following form

$$(\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{q(t)=x} D_n^+[q(t)] \Psi_0(q(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t); t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon. \quad (2.17)$$

For the limit in RHS of (2.16) and (2.17) we will be used following path integral notation

$$(\Psi_\varepsilon(t, x))_\varepsilon = \left(\int_{q(t)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi_0(q(0)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t)) \right] \right)_\varepsilon. \quad (2.18)$$

Let us consider now regularized oscillatory integral

$$(J_{\varepsilon, n}(t; \hbar))_\varepsilon = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^d} \dots \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} dx_0 dx_1 \dots dx_n f(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n) \Psi_0(x_0) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n; t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon. \quad (2.19)$$

Lemma 2.1. (Localization Principle [25]-[26]) Let Ω be a domain in $\mathbb{R}^{d \times n}$ and $f \in C_0^\infty(\Omega)$ be a smooth function of compact support, $S_\varepsilon \in C^\infty(\Omega)$, $\varepsilon \in (0, 1]$ be a real valued smooth function without stationary points in $\text{supp}(f)$, i.e. $\partial_x S_\varepsilon(x) \neq 0$ for $x \in \Omega$. Let L be a differential operator

$$L(f) = - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(|S'_{\varepsilon, x}(x)|^{-2} \frac{\partial S_\varepsilon}{\partial x_i} f \right). \quad (2.20)$$

Then

$$(|J_{\varepsilon, n}(t; \hbar)|)_\varepsilon \leq \hbar \int_\Omega L(f(x)) dx. \quad \forall n, m \in \mathbb{N}, \forall \hbar \leq 1 \text{ there exist } c_m \text{ such that}$$

$$(J_{\varepsilon, n}(t; \hbar))_\varepsilon \leq c_m \hbar^m \|f\|, \quad \|f\| = \sup_{x \in \Omega} \sum_{|\alpha| \leq m} |D^\alpha f|. \quad (2.21)$$

Lemma 2.2. (Generalized Localization Principle) Let Ω_n be a domain in $\mathbb{R}^{d \times n}$ and $f_n \in C_0^\infty(\Omega_n)$ be a real valued smooth function without stationary points in $\text{supp}(f)$, i.e. $\partial_x S_\varepsilon(x) \neq 0$ for $x \in \Omega_n$

and let $(\varphi_\varepsilon(t; \hbar))_\varepsilon$ be infinite sequence $n \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\varphi_{\varepsilon, n}(t; \hbar))_\varepsilon = \\ & \left(\left(\frac{nm}{4\pi i \hbar} \right)^{d(n+1)/2} \int_{\Omega_n} dx_0 dx_1 \dots dx_n f_n(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n) \Psi_0(x_0) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\varepsilon(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_n; t) \right] \right)_\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

Then there exist infinite sequence $\{\hbar_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \hbar_k = 0$ such that

$$\left(\lim_{\substack{n \rightarrow \infty \\ k \rightarrow \infty}} \varphi_{\varepsilon, n}(t; \hbar_k) \right)_\varepsilon = 0.$$

Proof. Equality (2.23) immediately follows from (2.21).

Remark 2.1. From Lemma 2.2 follows that stationary phase approximation is not a valid asymptotic approximation in the limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ for a path-integral (2.14) and (2.18).

3. Exactquasi-classical asymptotic beyond Maslov canonical operator

Theorem3.1. Let us consider Cauchy problem (2.8) with initial data $\Psi_0(x)$ is given via formula

$$\Psi_0(x) = \frac{\eta^{d/4}}{(2\pi)^{d/4} \hbar^{d/4}} \exp\left[-\frac{\eta(x-x_0)^2}{2\hbar}\right], (3.1)$$

where $0 < \hbar \ll \eta \ll 1$ and $x^2 = \langle x, x \rangle$.

- (1) We assume now that: (i) $(V_\varepsilon(x, t))_\varepsilon \in G(\mathbb{R}^d)$, (ii) $V_{\varepsilon=0}(x, t) = V(x, t): \mathbb{R}_+ \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and
 (iii) $\forall t \in \mathbb{R}_+$ function $V(x, t)$ is a polynomial on variable $x = (x_1, \dots, x_d)$, i.e.

$$V(x, t) = \sum_{\|\alpha\| \leq m} g_\alpha(t) x^\alpha, \alpha = (i_1, \dots, i_d), x^\alpha = x_1^{i_1} \times \dots \times x_d^{i_d}, \|\alpha\| = \sum_{r=1}^d i_r (3.2)$$

- (2) Let $u(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y) = (u_1(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y), \dots, u_d(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y))$ be the solution of the boundary problem

$$\frac{\partial^2 u^T(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y)}{\partial \tau^2} = \text{Hess}[V(\lambda, \tau)] u^T(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y) + [V'(\lambda, \tau)]^T, (3.3)$$

$$u(0, t, \lambda, x, y) = y, u(t, t, \lambda, x, y) = x. (3.4)$$

Here $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d, u^T(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y) = (u_1(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y), \dots, u_d(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y))^T,$

$$V'(\lambda, \tau) = \left(\left[\frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x_1} \right]_{x=\lambda}, \dots, \left[\frac{\partial V(x, t)}{\partial x_d} \right]_{x=\lambda} \right) \text{ and } \text{Hess}[V(\lambda, \tau)] = \left[\frac{\partial^2 V(x, t)}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} \right]_{x=\lambda} (3.5)$$

- (3) Let $S(t, \lambda, x, y)$ be the *master action* given via formula

$$S(t, \lambda, x, y) = \int_0^t L(\dot{u}(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y), u(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y), \tau) d\tau, (3.6)$$

Where *master Lagrangian* $L(\dot{u}, u, \tau)$ are

$$L(\dot{u}, u, \tau) = \frac{m}{2} \dot{u}^2(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y) - \hat{V}(u(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y), \tau), \dot{u} = \left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \tau}, \dots, \frac{\partial u_d}{\partial \tau} \right), \dot{u}^2 = \langle \dot{u}, \dot{u} \rangle, (3.7)$$

$$\hat{V}((\tau, t, \lambda, x, y), \tau) = u(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y) \text{Hess}[V(\lambda, \tau)] u^T(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y) + V'(\lambda, \tau) u^T(\tau, t, \lambda, x, y). (3.8)$$

Let $y_{cr} = y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be solution of the linear system of the algebraic equations

$$\left[\frac{\partial S(t, \lambda, x, y)}{\partial y_i} \right]_{y=y_{cr}} = 0, i = 1, \dots, d (3.9)$$

- (4) Let $\hat{x} = \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be solution of the linear system of the algebraic equations

$$y_{cr}(t, \lambda, \hat{x}) + \lambda - x_0 = 0. \quad (3.10)$$

Assume that: for a given values of the parameters t, λ, x_0 the point $\hat{x} = \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0)$ is not a focal point on a corresponding trajectory is given by corresponding solution of the boundary problem (3.3). Then for the limiting quantum average given via formulae (1.1) the inequality is satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{\substack{\hbar \rightarrow 0 \\ \varepsilon \rightarrow 0}} |\langle i, t, x_0; \hbar \rangle - \lambda_i| \leq \\ & \leq 2 \left[\left| \det S_{y_{cr} y_{cr}} \left(t, \lambda, \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0), y_{cr}(t, \lambda, \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0)) \right) \right| \right]^{-1} |\hat{x}_i(t, \lambda, x_0)|, i = 1, \dots, d. \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

Thus one can calculate the limiting quantum trajectory corresponding to potential $V(x, t)$ by using *transcendental masterequation*

$$\hat{x}_i(t, \lambda, x_0) = 0, i = 1, \dots, d. \quad (3.12)$$

Proof. From inequality (A.15) and Theorem A1, using inequalities (A.53.a) and (A.53.b) we obtain

$$\lim_{\substack{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0 \\ \sigma \rightarrow 0}} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} |\langle \hat{x}_i, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon \rangle - \lambda_i| \leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} [\mathcal{R}_1(T, \lambda) + \mathcal{R}_2(T, \lambda)], i = 1, \dots, d. \quad (3.13)$$

where

$$\mathcal{R}_1(T, \lambda) = \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2, \quad (3.14)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_2(T, \lambda) = \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2. \quad (3.15)$$

We note that

$$\mathcal{R}_1(T, \lambda) = \int dx [\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, T, \lambda)]^2, \quad \mathcal{R}_2(T, \lambda) = \int dx [\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_2(x, T, \lambda)]^2, \quad (3.16)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, T, \lambda) &= \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] = \\ &= \int dy \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] = \int dy \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, y, T, \lambda), \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, y, T, \lambda) = \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \quad (3.18)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_2(x, T, \lambda) &= \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] = \\ &= \int dy \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] = \int dy \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_2(x, y, T, \lambda), \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_2(x, y, T, \lambda) = \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right].(3.20)$$

From Eq.(3.18) one obtain

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, y, T, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, y, T, \lambda) + \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, y, T, \lambda)],(3.21)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, y, T, \lambda) = \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right],(3.22)$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, y, T, \lambda) = \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right].(3.23)$$

Let us calculate now path integral $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, y, T, \lambda)$ and path integral $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, y, T, \lambda)$, using stationary phase approximation. From Eq.(A.23) follows directly that action $\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)$ coincide with *master action* $S(t, \lambda, x, y)$ is given via formulae (3.6)-(3.8) and therefore from Eq.(3.22) and Eq.(3.23) one obtain

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, y, T, \lambda) = \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] =$$

$$= \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, y, T, \lambda) = [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \Psi(y) \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}S(t, \lambda, x, y)\right](3.24)$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, y, T, \lambda) = \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] =$$

$$= \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, y, T, \lambda) = [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \Psi(y) \exp\left[-\frac{i}{\hbar}S(t, \lambda, x, y)\right].(3.25)$$

From Eq.(3.17) and Eq.(3.24) we obtain

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, T, \lambda) = \int dy \tilde{\mathcal{R}}_1(x, y, T, \lambda).(3.26)$$

Substitution Eq.(3.25) into Eq.(3.26) gives

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, T, \lambda) = [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \int dy \Psi(y) \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar}S(t, \lambda, x, y)\right].(3.26)$$

Similarly one obtain

$$\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, T, \lambda) = [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \int dy \Psi(y) \exp\left[-\frac{i}{\hbar}S(t, \lambda, x, y)\right].(3.27)$$

Let us calculate now integral $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,1}(x, T, \lambda)$ and integral $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}_{1,2}(x, T, \lambda)$ using stationary phase approximation. Let $y_{cr} = y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ be the stationary point of master action $S(t, \lambda, x, y)$

International Journal of Recent advances in Physics (IJRAP) Vol.3, No.4, November 2014
and therefore Eq.(3.9) is satisfied. Having applied stationary phase
Approximation one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}_{1,1}(x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x), T, \lambda) = \\ [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-\frac{1}{2}} [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \Psi(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (3.28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}_{1,2}(x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x), T, \lambda) = \\ [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-\frac{1}{2}} [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \Psi(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \exp \left[-\frac{i}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.29)$$

Substitution Eq.(3.28)-Eq.(3.29) into Eq.(3.21) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}_1(x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x), T, \lambda) &= \frac{1}{2} [\mathfrak{R}_{1,1}(x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x), T, \lambda) + \mathfrak{R}_{1,2}(x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x), T, \lambda)] = \\ &= [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-\frac{1}{2}} [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \Psi(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \times \\ &\times \left\{ \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right] + \exp \left[-\frac{i}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right] \right\} = \\ &= [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-\frac{1}{2}} [|x_i|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \Psi(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.30)$$

Substitution Eq.(3.30) into Eq.(3.16) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_1(T, \lambda) &= \int dx \int dx [\mathfrak{R}_1(x, T, \lambda)]^2 = \\ &= \int dx [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-1} |x_i| \Psi^2(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \cos^2 \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

Similarly one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{R}_2(T, \lambda) &= \int dx \int dx [\mathfrak{R}_2(x, T, \lambda)]^2 = \\ &= \int dx [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-1} |x_i| \Psi^2(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \sin^2 \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} S(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

Therefore

$$\mathcal{R}(T, \lambda) = \mathcal{R}_1(T, \lambda) + \mathcal{R}_2(T, \lambda) = 2 \int dx [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-1} |x_i| \Psi^2(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x)). \quad (3.33)$$

Substitution Eq.(3.1) into Eq.(3.33) gives

$$\mathcal{R}(T, \lambda) = 2 \frac{\eta^{d/2}}{(2\pi)^{d/2} \hbar^{d/2}} \int dx [|\det S_{y_{cr}y_{cr}}(t, \lambda, x, y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x))|]^{-1} |x_i| \exp \left[-\frac{\eta(y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x) - x_0)^2}{\hbar} \right] \quad (3.34)$$

Let us calculate now integral (3.34) using Laplace's approximation. It is easy to see that corresponding stationary point $\hat{x} = \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the solution of the linear system of the algebraic equations(3.10). Therefore finally we obtain

$$\mathcal{R}(T, \lambda) = 2|\hat{x}_i(t, \lambda, x_0)| \left[\left| \det S_{y_{cr} y_{cr}} \left(t, \lambda, \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0), y_{cr}(t, \lambda, \hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0)) \right) \right| \right]^{-1} + O(\hbar^d),$$

$$i = 1, \dots, d. (3.35)$$

Substitution Eq.(3.35) into inequality (3.13) gives the inequality(3.11). The inequality (3.11) completed the proof.

4. Quantum an harmonic oscillator with a cubic potential supplemented by additive sinusoidal driving.

In this subsection we calculate exact quasi-classical asymptotic for quantum an harmonic oscillator with a cubic potential supplemented by additive sinusoidal driving. Using Theorem3.1 we obtain corresponding limiting quantum trajectories given via Eq.(1.3).

Let us consider quantum an harmonic oscillator with a cubic potential

$$V(x) = \frac{m\omega^2}{2}x^2 - ax^3 + bx, x \in \mathbb{R}, a, b > 0 (4.1)$$

supplemented by an additive sinusoidal driving. Thus

$$V(x, t) = \frac{m\omega^2}{2}x^2 - ax^3 + bx - [A \sin(\Omega t)]x. \quad (4.2)$$

The corresponding master Lagrangian given by(3.7),are

$$L(\dot{u}, u, \tau) = \left(\frac{m}{2}\right)\dot{u}^2 - m \left(\left(\frac{\omega^2}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{3a\lambda}{m}\right) \right) u^2 - (m\omega^2\lambda + 3a\lambda^2 - b - A \sin(\Omega t))u. (4.3)$$

We assume now that: $\frac{\omega^2}{2} + \frac{3a\lambda}{m} \geq 0$ and rewrite(4.3)of the form

$$L(\dot{u}, u, \tau) = (m/2)\dot{u}^2 - (m\varpi^2\lambda/2)u^2 + g(\lambda, t)u, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\varpi(\lambda) = \sqrt{2 \left| \frac{\omega^2}{2} + \frac{3a\lambda}{m} \right|}$ and $g(\lambda, t) = - [m\omega^2\lambda + 3a\lambda^2 - b - A \sin(\Omega \cdot t)]$.

The corresponding master action $S(t, \lambda, x, y)$ given by Eq.(3.6), are

$$S(t, \lambda, x, y) = \frac{m\varpi}{2\sin\varpi t} [(\cos\varpi t)(y^2 + x^2) - 2xy + \frac{2x}{m\varpi} \int_0^t g(\lambda, \tau) \sin(\varpi\tau) d\tau + \frac{2y}{m\varpi} \int_0^t g(\lambda, \tau) \sin(\varpi(t - \tau)) d\tau - \frac{2}{m^2\varpi^2} \int_0^t \int_0^\tau g(\lambda, \tau)g(\lambda, s) \sin\varpi(t - \tau) \sin(\varpi s) dsd\tau]. (4.5)$$

The linear system of the algebraic equations(3.9) are

$$\frac{\partial S(t, \lambda, x, y)}{\partial y} = 2y\cos\varpi t - 2x + \frac{2}{m\varpi} \int_0^t g(\lambda, \tau) \sin(\varpi(t - \tau)) d\tau = 0. \quad (4.6)$$

Therefore

$$y_{cr}(t, \lambda, x) = \frac{x}{\cos\varpi t} - \frac{1}{m\varpi\cos\varpi t} \int_0^t g(\lambda, \tau) \sin(\varpi(t - \tau)) d\tau \quad (4.7)$$

The linear system of the algebraic equations (3.10) are

$$\frac{x}{\cos\omega t} - \frac{1}{m\omega\cos\omega t} \int_0^t g(\lambda, t)\sin((\omega(t - \tau))d\tau + \lambda - x_0 = 0. \quad (4.8)$$

Therefore the solution of the linear system of the algebraic equations (3.10) are

$$\hat{x}(t, \lambda, x_0) = \frac{1}{m\omega} \int_0^t g(\lambda, t)\sin((\omega(t - \tau))d\tau + (\lambda(t) - x_0)\cos\omega t. \quad (4.9)$$

Transcendental master equation (3.11) are

$$\frac{1}{m\omega} \int_0^t g(\lambda(t), t)\sin((\omega(t - \tau))d\tau + (\lambda(t) - x_0)\cos\omega t = 0 \quad (4.10)$$

Finally from Eq.(4.10) one obtain

$$d(\lambda(t)) \left(\frac{\cos(\omega t)}{\omega} - \frac{1}{\omega} \right) + \frac{A(\omega\sin(\Omega t) - \Omega\sin(\omega t))}{\omega^2 - \Omega^2} - (\lambda(t) - x_0)m\omega\cos(\omega t) = 0, (4.11)$$

where $d(\lambda) = m\omega^2\lambda + 3a\lambda^2 - b$.

Numerical Examples.

Example 1. $x_0 = 0, m = 1, \Omega = 0, \omega = 9, a = 3, b = 10, A = 0$.

Pic.1. Limiting quantum trajectory $\lambda(t)$ Pic.2. Limiting quantum trajectory $\lambda(t)$ with a jump

5. Comparison exact quasi-classical asymptotic with stationary-point approximation.

We set now $d = 1$. Let us consider now path integral (2.14) with $S_\epsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t); t)$ given via formula

$$S_\epsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t) = \frac{1}{4} \int_0^t [\dot{q}(\tau) - F_\epsilon(q(\tau), \tau)]^2 d\tau. \quad (5.1)$$

Note that for corresponding propagator $K_\epsilon(x, t|y, 0)$ the time discretized path-integral representation

$K_{\epsilon,N}(x, t|y, 0)$ are :

$$K_{\epsilon,N}(x, t|y, 0) = \int \frac{dx_1 dx_2 \dots dx_{N-1}}{(4\pi\hbar\Delta t)^{N/2}} \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_{\epsilon,N}(x_0, \dots, x_N) \right], (5.2)$$

where $S_{\epsilon,N}(x_0, \dots, x_N)$ are :

$$S_{\varepsilon,N}(x_0, \dots, x_N) = \frac{\Delta t}{4} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \left[\frac{x_{n+1} - x_n}{\Delta t} - F_{\varepsilon}(x_n, t_n) \right]^2. \quad (5.3)$$

Here the initial- x_0 and end-points x_N are fixed by the prescribed x_0 and by the additional constraint $x_N = y$.

Let us calculate now integral (5.2) using stationary-point approximation. Denoting an critical points of the discrete-time action(5.3)by $\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k} = (x_{1,\varepsilon,k}, \dots, x_{N-1,\varepsilon,k})$ it follows that $\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}$ satisfies the critical point conditions are

$$\frac{\partial S_{\varepsilon,N}(x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, \dots, x_{N-1,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k})}{\partial x_{n,\varepsilon,k}} = 0 \quad (5.4)$$

for $n = 1, \dots, N - 1$, supplemented by the prescribed boundary conditions for $n = 0, n = N: x_{0,\varepsilon,k} = x_0,$

$$x_{N,\varepsilon,k} = x.$$

From Eq.(5.2) in the limit $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ using form all y Stationary-point approximation one obtain

$$K_{\varepsilon,N}(x, t|x_0, 0) \cong \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N-1}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) \right] + O(\hbar). \quad (5.5)$$

Here the pre-factor $\mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k})$ is given via N-dimensional Gaussian integral of the canonical form as

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N-1}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) = \int \frac{dy_1 dy_2 \dots dy_{N-1}}{(4\pi\hbar\Delta t)^{N/2}} \exp \left[\frac{i}{2\hbar} \sum_{n,m=1}^{N-1} y_n \frac{\partial^2 S_{\varepsilon,N}(x_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k})}{\partial x_{n,\varepsilon,k} \partial x_{m,\varepsilon,k}} y_m \right]. \quad (5.6)$$

The Gaussian integral in (5.6) is given via canonical formula

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N-1}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) = \left[4\pi\hbar\Delta t \det \left(2\Delta t \frac{\partial^2 S_{\varepsilon,N}(x_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k})}{\partial x_{n,\varepsilon,k} \partial x_{m,\varepsilon,k}} \right) \right]^{-1/2}, \quad n, m = 1, \dots, N - 1. \quad (5.7)$$

Here $\det(A_{n,m})$ denotethe determinant of an $N - 1 \times N - 1$ matrix with elements $A_{n,m}$.

Let us consider now Cauchy problem (2.8) with initial data $\Psi_0(x)$ is given via formula

$$\Psi_0(x) = \frac{\eta^{1/4}}{(2\pi)^{1/4} \hbar^{1/4}} \exp \left[-\frac{\eta(x - z_0)^2}{2\hbar} \right].$$

Note that for corresponding Colombeau solution $\Psi_{\varepsilon}(t, x)$ given viapath-integral(2.14)the time discretized path-integral representation $\Psi_{\varepsilon,N}(t, x)$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\varepsilon,N}(t, x) &= \int \Psi_0(x_0) K_{\varepsilon,N}(x, t|x_0, 0) dx_0 = \\ &= \sum_k \int dx_0 \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N-1}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_0, x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) \Psi_0(x_0) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} S_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_0, x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) \right] [1 + O(\hbar)]. \quad (5.8) \end{aligned}$$

Let us calculate now integrals in RHS of Eq.(5.8) using stationary-point approximation. Corresponding critical point conditions are

$$\frac{\partial S_{\varepsilon,N}(x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, \dots, x_{N-1,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,k})}{\partial x_{0,\varepsilon,k}} = 0. \quad (5.9)$$

From (5.8) we obtain

$$\Psi_{\varepsilon,N}(t, x) = \sum_k \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x) \Psi_0(x_{0,\varepsilon,k}) \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x) \right] [1 + O(\hbar)]. \quad (5.10)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x) = \left[\Delta t \det \left(2\Delta t \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x)}{\partial x_{n,\varepsilon,k} \partial x_{m,\varepsilon,k}} \right) \right]^{-1/2}, \quad n, m = 0, 1, \dots, N-1. \quad (5.11)$$

Let as denote $\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,0} = (x_{0,\varepsilon,0}, x_{1,\varepsilon,0}, \dots, x_{N-1,\varepsilon,0}) = (x_{0,\varepsilon,0}(x), x_{1,\varepsilon,0}(x), \dots, x_{N-1,\varepsilon,0}(x))$ the critical point for which the critical point conditions(5.4) are

$$\frac{x_{n+1,\varepsilon,0} - x_{n,\varepsilon,0}}{\Delta t} - F_{\varepsilon}(x_{n,\varepsilon,0}, t_n) = 0, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N-1. \quad (5.12)$$

Therefore the time discretized path-integral representation of the Colom beau quantum averages given by Eq. (1.1) are

$$\begin{aligned} ((1, t, z_0; \hbar, \varepsilon))_{\varepsilon} &= \left(\int x |\Psi_{\varepsilon,N}(x, t; \hbar)|^2 dx \right)_{\varepsilon} \\ &= \frac{\eta^{1/2}}{(2\pi)^{1/2} \hbar^{1/2}} \left(\int dx x \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}^2(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,0}, x) \exp \left[-\frac{\eta(x_{0,\varepsilon,0}(x) - z_0)^2}{\hbar} \right] \right)_{\varepsilon} [1 + O(\hbar^2)] + \\ &+ \frac{\eta^{1/2}}{(2\pi)^{1/2} \hbar^{1/2}} \left(\sum_{k \geq 1} \int dx x \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}^2(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,0}, x) \exp \left[-\frac{\eta(x_{0,\varepsilon,0}(x) - z_0)^2}{\hbar} \right] \right)_{\varepsilon} [1 + O(\hbar^2)] + O(\exp(-c\hbar^{-1})), \end{aligned} \quad (5.13)$$

where $c > 0, \varepsilon \in (0, 1], x \in \mathbb{R}$. Let us calculate now integrals in RHS of Eq.(5.13) using stationary-point approximation. Corresponding critical point conditions are

$$x_{0,\varepsilon,0}(x_{N,\varepsilon,0}) - z_0 = 0, \quad (5.14).$$

$$x_{0,\varepsilon,k}(x_{N,\varepsilon,k}) - z_0 = 0, \quad k \geq 1. \quad (5.15).$$

Here $x_{N,\varepsilon,0}$ can be calculated using linear recursion(5.12) with initial data $x_{0,\varepsilon,0} = z_0$.

From Eq.(5.13)-Eq.(5.14) one obtain

$$((1, t, z_0; \hbar, \varepsilon))_{\varepsilon} \cong \left(x_{N,\varepsilon,0} \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}^2(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,0}, x_{N,\varepsilon,0}) \right)_{\varepsilon} \quad (5.16)$$

$$\text{and } \mathbf{Z}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,0}) = \left[\Delta t \det \left(2\Delta t \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,N}(\mathbf{x}_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,0})}{\partial x_{n,\varepsilon,k} \partial x_{m,\varepsilon,k}} \right) \right]^{-1/2}, \quad n, m = 0, 1, \dots, N. \quad (5.17)$$

As demonstrated in [24] the determinant appearing in(5.11) can be calculated using second Order linear recursion:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Q_{n+1,\varepsilon,k} - 2Q_{n,\varepsilon,k} - Q_{n-1,\varepsilon,k}}{(\Delta t)^2} &= 2 \frac{Q_{n,\varepsilon,k} F'_x(x_{n,\varepsilon,k}, t_n) - Q_{n-1,\varepsilon,k} F'_x(x_{n-1,\varepsilon,k}, t_{n-1})}{\Delta t} - \\ &- Q_{n,\varepsilon,k} \left[\frac{x_{n+1,\varepsilon,k} - x_{n,\varepsilon,k}}{\Delta t} - F_{\varepsilon}(x_{n,\varepsilon,k}, t_n) \right] F''_{\varepsilon,x^2}(x_{n,\varepsilon,k}, t_n) + \\ &+ Q_{n,\varepsilon,k} [F'_{\varepsilon,x}(x_{n,\varepsilon,k}, t_n)]^2 - Q_{n-1,\varepsilon,k} [F'_{\varepsilon,x}(x_{n-1,\varepsilon,k}, t_{n-1})]^2, \end{aligned}$$

$$F'_{\varepsilon,x}(x, t) = \frac{\partial F_{\varepsilon}(x, t)}{\partial x}, \quad F''_{\varepsilon,x}(x, t) = \frac{\partial^2 F_{\varepsilon}(x, t)}{\partial x^2}. \quad (5.18)$$

International Journal of Recent advances in Physics (IJRAP) Vol.3, No.4, November 2014
with initial data $Q_{1,\varepsilon,k} = \Delta t, Q_{2,\varepsilon,k} = Q_{1,\varepsilon,k} + \Delta t + O((\Delta t)^2)$ (5.19)

from which the pre-factor $Z_{\varepsilon,N}(x_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,0})$ in (5.16) follows as

$$Z_{\varepsilon,N}(x_{\varepsilon,k}, x_{0,\varepsilon,k}, x_{N,\varepsilon,0}) = \sqrt{Q_{N,\varepsilon,k}}.(5.20)$$

In the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ from critical point conditions (5.12) and (5.14) one obtain

$$\dot{x}(t) - F_{\varepsilon}(x(t), t) = 0, x(0) = z_0.(5.21)$$

In the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ from a second order linear recursion(5.18)one obtain the second order linear differential equation

$$\ddot{Q}_{\varepsilon,0}(t) = 2 \frac{d}{dt} [Q_{\varepsilon,0}(t) F'_{\varepsilon,x}(x(t), t)](5.22)$$

with initial data

$$Q_{\varepsilon,0}(0) = 0, \dot{Q}_{\varepsilon,0}(0) = 1.(5.23)$$

By integration Eq.(5.22) one obtain the first order linear differential equation

$$\dot{Q}_{\varepsilon,0}(t) = 2Q_{\varepsilon,0}(t) F'_{\varepsilon,x}(x(t), t) + 1, Q_{\varepsilon,0}(0) = 0.(5.24)$$

In the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ from Eq.(5.16), Eq.(5.20)-Eq.(5.21) and Eq.(5.24)one obtain

$$E(t) = (\langle 1, t, z_0; \hbar, \varepsilon \rangle)_{\varepsilon} \cong x(t) Q_{\varepsilon,0}^{-2}(t).(5.25)$$

We set now in Eq.(5.1)

$$F_{\varepsilon}(q, \tau) = -aq^3 + bx + A \sin(\Omega\tau).(5.26)$$

Corresponding differential master equation are

$$\dot{q} = -(3a\lambda^2 - b)q - (a\lambda^3 - b\lambda) + A \sin(\Omega\tau), q(0) = z_0 - \lambda.(5.27)$$

From Eq.(5.27) one obtain that corresponding transcendental master equation are

$$[z_0 - \lambda(t)] - \frac{\Delta[\lambda(t)]}{\Theta[\lambda(t)]} \{ \exp(t\Delta[\lambda(t)]) - 1 \} + A \frac{\exp(t\Delta[\lambda(t)])}{\Omega^2 + \Theta^2[\lambda(t)]} \{ \Theta[\lambda(t)] \sin(\Omega t) - \Omega \cos(\Omega t) \} + A \frac{\Omega}{\Omega^2 + \Theta^2[\lambda(t)]} = 0.(5.28)$$

Numerical Examples.

Comparison of the: (1)classical dynamics calculated by using Eq.(5.1) (red curve), (2)limiting quantum trajectory $\lambda(t)$ calculated by using master equation Eq.(5.28) (blue curve) and (3) limiting quantum trajectory calculated by using stationary-point approximation given by Eq.(5.25)(green curve).

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Pic.3.Limiting quantum trajectory $\lambda(t)$ Pic.4.Limiting quantum trajectory $\lambda(t)$ without jumps. $a = 0.3, b = 1, A = 2$.witha jump. $a = 1, b = 1, A = 0.3$.

4. Conclusions

We pointed out that there exist limiting quantum trajectories given via Eq.(1.3) with a jumps. Such jumps does not depend on any single measurement of particle position $q(t)$ at instant t and obtained without any reference to a phenomenological master-equation of Lind blad form. An axiom of quantum mechanics is that we cannot predict the result of any single measurement of an observable of a quantum mechanical system in a super position of eigen states. However we can predict the result of any single measurement of particle position $q(t)$ at instant t with a probability $P(t, q, \delta q) \cong 1$ if valid the condition: $\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\|\delta q(t)\| \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} P_t(q(t), \delta q(t), x_0; \hbar, \varepsilon) = 1$, where P_t given via Eq.(1.5).

5. Acknowledgments

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Appendix

Let us consider now regularized Feynman- Colombeau propagator $(K_\varepsilon(x, T|y, 0))_\varepsilon$ given by Feynman path integral:

$$\tilde{K}_\varepsilon(x, T|y, 0; \sigma, l) = \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(q, T; \sigma, l) \right] \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_2(q(T), \lambda) \right] \exp \left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T) \right], (A.1)$$

where $\hbar \in (0, 1]$,

$$\mathcal{S}_1(q, T; \sigma, l) = \int_0^T dt \{ [q(t) - \lambda]^2; \sigma, l \}, (A.2)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_2(q(T), \lambda) = [q(T) - \lambda]^2, \lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_d) \in \mathbb{R}^d, (A.3)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T) = \int_0^T L(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t) dt, L(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t) = \frac{m}{2} \dot{q}^2(t) - V_\varepsilon(q(t), t), V_{\varepsilon=0}(x, t) = V(x, t), (A.4)$$

$$V(x, t) = g_1(t)x + g_2(t)x^2 + g_3(t)x^3 + \dots + g_\alpha(t)x^\alpha, (A.5)$$

$$\alpha = (i_1, \dots, i_d), x^\alpha = x_1^{i_1} \times \dots \times x_d^{i_d}, \|\alpha\| = \sum_{r=1}^d i_r,$$

$$V_\varepsilon(q(t), t) = V(q_\varepsilon(t), t), q_\varepsilon(t) = (q_{1,\varepsilon}(t), \dots, q_{d,\varepsilon}(t)), \text{(A.6)}$$

$$q_{i,\varepsilon}(t) = \frac{q_i(t)}{1 + \varepsilon^{2k} |q(t)|^{2k}}, \varepsilon \in (0, 1], k \geq 1. \text{(A.7)}$$

Here: (1) $\sigma \in (0, 1], \hbar \ll \sigma$ and (2) for each path $q(t)$ such that $q(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi t}{T}\right) + u(t, T, y, x), u(0, T, y, x) = y, u(T, T, y, x) = x$, where $u(t, T, y, x)$ is a given function, operator $\{p(t); \sigma, l\}$ are

$$\{q(t); \sigma, l\} = \sum_{n=1}^l \sigma a_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi t}{T}\right) + \sum_{n=l+1}^{\infty} a_n \sin\left(\frac{n\pi t}{T}\right). \text{(A.8)}$$

(3) $D^+[q(t)]$ is a positive Feynman “measure”.

Therefore regularized Colombeau solution of the Schrödinger equation corresponding to regularized propagator (A.1) are

$$\begin{aligned} (\Psi_\varepsilon(T, x; \sigma, l, \lambda))_\varepsilon &= \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \Psi(y) \tilde{R}_\varepsilon(x, T | y, 0; \sigma, l) \right)_\varepsilon = \\ &= \left(\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda)\right] \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T)\right] \right)_\varepsilon = \\ &= \left(\int dy \int_{q(0)=y}^{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda)\right] \exp\left[\frac{i}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T)\right] \right)_\varepsilon. \text{(A.9)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Here } \mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda) = \mathbf{S}_1(q, T; \sigma, l) + \mathbf{S}_2(q(T), \lambda). \text{(A.10)}$$

Let us consider now regularized quantum average

$$\langle (\hat{x}_i, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) \rangle_\varepsilon = \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx x_i |\Psi_\varepsilon(T, x; \sigma, l, \lambda)|^2 \right)_\varepsilon. \text{(A.11)}$$

From (A.5) and (A.11) one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle (\hat{x}_i, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) \rangle_\varepsilon \\ & \leq \left(\int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T)\right] \right\}^2 \right)_\varepsilon + \\ & + \left(\int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T)\right] \right\}^2 \right)_\varepsilon \text{(A.13)} \end{aligned}$$

From Eq.(A.5)-(A.13) one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & |\langle \hat{x}_i, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon \rangle - \lambda_i| = \left| \langle \hat{x}_i, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon \rangle - \lambda_i \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx |\Psi_\varepsilon(T, x; \sigma, l, \lambda)|^2 \right| = \\ & = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx [x_i - \lambda_i] |\Psi_\varepsilon(T, x; \sigma, l, \lambda)|^2 \right| \leq \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx |x_i - \lambda_i| |\Psi_\varepsilon(T, x; \sigma, l, \lambda)|^2 = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T) - \lambda_i|]^{1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda) \right] \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T) \right] \right\}^2 + \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T) - \lambda_i|]^{1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l, \lambda) \right] \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q, T) \right] \right\}^2 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Using replacement $q_i(t) - \lambda_i := q_i(t), i = 1, \dots, d$ into RHS of the Eq.(A.9) one obtain

$$|\langle \hat{x}_i, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon \rangle - \lambda_i| \leq \leq \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l) \right] \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q + \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2 + \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l) \right] \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q + \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2 = = \int dx [I_1^2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)] + \int dx [I_2^2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)]. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Here

$$\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l) = \mathcal{S}_1(q, T; \sigma, l) + \mathcal{S}_2(q(T)), \mathcal{S}_1(q, T; \sigma, l) = \int_0^T dt \{ [q(t)]^2; \sigma, l \},$$

$$\mathcal{S}_2(q(T)) = [q(T)]^2, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^d \quad (\text{A.16})$$

and

$$I_1(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) = \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l) \right] \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q + \lambda, T) \right] \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$I_2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) = \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l) \right] \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_\varepsilon(\dot{q}, q + \lambda, T) \right]. \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Let us rewrite a function $V_\varepsilon(q(t) + \lambda, t)$ in the following equivalent form:

$$V_\varepsilon(q(t) + \lambda, t) = V_{\varepsilon,0}(q(t), t, \lambda) + V_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda), \quad (\text{A.19})$$

$$V_{\varepsilon,0}(q(t), t, \lambda) = a_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda)q(t) + a_{\varepsilon,2}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^2(t), \quad (\text{A.20})$$

$$V_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda) = a_{\varepsilon,3}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^3(t) + \dots + a_{\varepsilon,\alpha}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^\alpha(t), \quad (\text{A.21})$$

where $a_{\varepsilon=0,1}(q(t), t, \lambda) = c_1(t, \lambda), a_{\varepsilon=0,2}(q(t), t, \lambda) = c_2(t, \lambda), \dots, a_{\varepsilon=0,\alpha}(q(t), t, \lambda) = c_\alpha(t, \lambda)$.

Let us evaluate now path integral $I_1(T; \sigma, l, \lambda)$ given via Eq.(A.17). Substitution Eq.(A.19) into RHS of the Eq.(A.17) gives

$$I_1(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) = I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) + I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q + \lambda, T)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q + \lambda, T)\right] +$$

$$+ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \sin\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right],$$

(A.22.a)

$$I_2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) = I_2^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) + I_2^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q + \lambda, T)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q + \lambda, T)\right] +$$

$$+ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \cos\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right],$$

(A.22.b)

where

$$\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) = \int_0^T L_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t, \lambda) dt, L_\varepsilon(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t, \lambda) = \frac{m}{2}\dot{q}^2(t) - V_{\varepsilon,0}(q(t), t, \lambda),$$

(A.23)

$$\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T) = \int_0^T V_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda) dt,$$

(A.24)

$$I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right],$$

(A.25.a)

$$I_2^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right],$$

(A.25.b)

$$I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \sin\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right].$$

(A.26.a)

$$I_2^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \cos\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right].$$

(A.26.b)

Let us evaluate nown-dimensional path integral $I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$:

$$I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right] = \\
 &= \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \left\{ \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + 1 \right\} \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right] - \\
 &- \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right]. \quad (\text{A.27})
 \end{aligned}$$

From Eq.(A.27) one obtain the inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)| \\
 &\leq \left| \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \left\{ \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] + 1 \right\} \right| - \\
 &- \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right] = \\
 &= \left| \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \right| + \\
 &\quad + \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] - \\
 &- \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right]. \quad (\text{A.28})
 \end{aligned}$$

From Inq.(A.28) one obtain the inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)| \leq \left| \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \right| - \\
 &- \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \hbar^{-2i}}{(2i)!} \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} [\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)]^{2i} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] = \\
 &= |\mathbf{J}_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)| - \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \hbar^{-2i}}{(2i)!} \mathcal{R}_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n), \quad (\text{A.29})
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\mathbf{J}_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) =$$

$$= \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))\left[|q_i(T)|\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \cos\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right], \text{(A.30)}$$

$$\mathcal{R}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) = \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))\left[|q_i(T)|\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right]^{2i} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right]. \text{(A.31)}$$

Using replacement $q_i(t) := \hbar^{\frac{1}{2}}\bar{q}_i(t), t \in [0, T], i = 1, \dots, d$ into RHS of the Eq.(A.31) one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{R}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) \\ &= \hbar^{1/4} \int_{q(T)=\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}}} \bar{D}_n^+[q(t)]\Psi\left(\hbar^{\frac{1}{2}}q(0)\right)\left[|q_i(T)|\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(\hbar^{1/2}q, \lambda, T)\right]^{2i} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathbf{S}(\hbar^{1/2}q, T; \sigma, l)\right] = \end{aligned}$$

$$\hbar^{1/4}\hbar^{i/2} \int_{\substack{q(T)=\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}} \\ q(0)=\frac{y}{\sqrt{\hbar}}}} dy \int \bar{D}_n^+[q(t)]\bar{\Psi}(q(0))\left[|q_i(T)|\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T, \hbar)\right]^{2i} \exp[-\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)] =$$

$$= \hbar^{1/4}\hbar^{i/2}\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n), \text{where(A.32)}$$

$$\bar{D}_n^+[q(t)] = D_n^+\left[\hbar^{\frac{1}{2}}q(t)\right], t \in [0, T], \bar{\Psi}(q(0)) = \frac{\eta^{d/4}}{(2\pi)^{d/4}\hbar^{d/4}} \exp\left[\frac{\eta q^2(0)}{2}\right], \text{see Eq.(3.1) and}$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T, \hbar) = \int_0^T \widehat{V}_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda, \hbar) dt, \text{(A.33)}$$

$$\widehat{V}_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda, \hbar) = a_{\varepsilon,3}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^3(t) + \dots + \hbar^{\frac{\alpha-3}{2}}a_{\varepsilon,\alpha}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^\alpha(t). \text{(A.34)}$$

$$\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) = \int dy \int_{\substack{q(T)=\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}} \\ q(0)=\frac{y}{\sqrt{\hbar}}}} \bar{D}_n^+[q(t)]\bar{\Psi}(q(0))\left[|q_i(T)|\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\widehat{\mathbf{S}}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T, \hbar)\right]^{2i} \exp[-\mathbf{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)]. \text{(A.35)}$$

From (A.29)-(A.35) one obtain

$$\left|I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)\right| \leq \left|I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)\right| - \hbar^{\frac{1}{4}} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \hbar^i}{(2i)!} \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) =$$

$$\leq \left|I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)\right| - \hbar^{\frac{1}{4}}\mathfrak{E}_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, n), \text{where(A.36)}$$

$$\mathfrak{E}_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar, n) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \hbar^i}{(2i)!} \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n). \text{(A.37)}$$

Proposition A.1.[21]-[23] Let $\{S_{n,m}\}_{n,m=1}^{n,m=\infty}$ be a double sequences: $\mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. Let $\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} S_{n,m} = a$.

Then the iterated limit: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} S_{n,m})$ exist and equal to a if and only if $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} S_{n,m}$ exists for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proposition A.2. Let $I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) = I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$, where $I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$ is given via

International Journal of Recent advances in Physics (IJRAP) Vol.3, No.4, November 2014
 Eq.(A.25) and let $I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) = I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$, where $I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$ is given via

Eq.(A.26). Then $I_2^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) =$

- (1) $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)]^2 \leq$

$$\leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2,$$
- (2) $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)]^2 = 0,$
- (3) $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)] = 0,$
- (4) $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_2^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)]^2 \leq$

$$\leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2,$$
- (5) $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_2^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)]^2 = 0,$
- (6) $\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_2^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) I_2^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)] = 0.$

Here

$$\mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) = \mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon=0,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) = \int_0^T L_{\varepsilon=0}(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t, \lambda) dt,$$

$$L_{\varepsilon=0}(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t, \lambda) = \frac{m}{2} \dot{q}^2(t) - V_{\varepsilon=0,0}(q(t), t, \lambda).$$

Proof(I) Let us to choose an sequence $\{\hbar_m\}_{m=1}^{\infty}$ such that

- (i) $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \hbar_m = 0$ and
- (ii) $\lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ \Xi_{\varepsilon}^{(m)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2 = \lim_{m, n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{(-1)^i \hbar_m^i}{(2i)!} \hat{\mathcal{R}}_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) \right\}^2 = 0.$

We note that from (ii) follows that: perturbative expansion

$$\int dx \left\{ \Xi_{\varepsilon}(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2 = \hbar_m^{1/4} \int dx \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i \hbar_m^i}{(2i)!} \hat{\mathcal{R}}_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) \right\}^2$$

International Journal of Recent advances in Physics (IJRAP) Vol.3, No.4, November 2014
 vanishes in the limit $m, n \rightarrow \infty$. From (A.36) and Schwarz's inequality using Proposition A.1, one obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m)]^2 \\
 & \leq \underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ |J_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m)| - \hbar_m^{1/4} \Xi_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar, n) \right\}^2 \\
 & \leq \overline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ J_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m) \right\}^2 + \\
 & + \underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ 2 \hbar_m^{1/4} \sqrt{\int dx \left\{ J_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m) \right\}^2 \int dx \left\{ \Xi_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2} \right. \\
 & \left. + \int dx \left\{ \Xi_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2 \right\} \\
 & = \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ J_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m) \right\}^2 = \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ J_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) \right\}^2 = \\
 & = \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2. \text{(A.38)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let us to choose now an subsequence $\{\hbar_{m_k}\}_{m_k=1}^\infty$ such that the limit:

$$\lim_{k,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k})]^2 \text{ exist and } \lim_{k,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k})]^2 =$$

$$\underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m)]^2 \text{(A.39)}$$

From (A.39) and Proposition A.1 one obtain

$$\lim_{k,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k})]^2 = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k})]^2 \right\}. \text{(A.40)}$$

From (A.39),(A.40) and(A.38)one obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underline{\lim}_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)]^2 \leq \\
 & \leq \underline{\lim}_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_{1,n}^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k})]^2 \right\} = \\
 & = \underline{\lim}_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k})]^2 \leq \\
 & \leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2. \text{(A.41)}
 \end{aligned}$$

The inequality (A.41) completed the proof of the statement (1).

(II) Let us estimate now n -dimensional path integral

$$I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) = \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \sin\left[\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T)\right] \sin\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right]. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

From Eq. (A.42) one obtain the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & |I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)| \leq \\ & \leq \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] \left| \sin\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)\right] \right| \leq \\ & \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hbar^{-(2i+1)}}{(2i+1)!} \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} [|\mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)|]^{(2i+1)} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right] = \\ & = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hbar^{-(2i+1)}}{(2i+1)!} \wp_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) \quad (\text{A.43}) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\wp_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) = \int_{q(T)=x} D_n^+[q(t)]\Psi(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} [|\mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)|]^{(2i+1)} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)\right]. \quad (\text{A.44})$$

Using replacement $q_i(t) := \hbar^{\frac{1}{2}}\tilde{q}_i(t), t \in [0, T], i = 1, \dots, d$ into RHS of the Eq.(A.44) one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \wp_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) = \\ & \hbar^{1/4} \int_{q(T)=\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}}} \tilde{D}_n^+[q(t)]\Psi\left(\hbar^{\frac{1}{2}}q(0)\right)[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} [|\mathcal{S}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)|]^{(2i+1)} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{\hbar}\mathcal{S}(\hbar^{1/2}q, T; \sigma, l)\right] = \\ & \hbar^{1/4}\hbar^{i/2} \int_{\substack{q(T)=\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}} \\ q(0)=\frac{y}{\sqrt{\hbar}}}} dy \int \tilde{D}_n^+[q(t)]\tilde{\Psi}(q(0))[|q_i(T)|]^{1/2} [|\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)|]^{(2i+1)} \exp[-\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)] = \\ & = \hbar^{1/4}\hbar^{i/2}\hat{\wp}_{\varepsilon}^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n), \text{where} \quad (\text{A.45}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{D}_n^+[q(t)] = D_n^+\left[\hbar^{\frac{1}{2}}q(t)\right], t \in [0, T], \tilde{\Psi}(q(0)) = \frac{\eta^{d/4}}{(2\pi)^{d/4}\hbar^{d/4}} \exp\left[\frac{\eta q^2(0)}{2}\right], \text{see Eq.(3.1) and}$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T, \hbar) = \int_0^T \hat{V}_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda, \hbar) dt, \quad (\text{A.46})$$

$$\hat{V}_{\varepsilon,1}(q(t), t, \lambda, \hbar) = a_{\varepsilon,3}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^3(t) + \dots + \hbar^{\frac{\alpha-3}{2}} a_{\varepsilon,\alpha}(q(t), t, \lambda)q^\alpha(t). \quad (\text{A.47})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\phi}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) = \\ \int dy \int_{q(T)=\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}}}^{\frac{x}{\sqrt{\hbar}}} \bar{D}_n^+[q(t)] \bar{\Psi}(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} [|\hat{\mathcal{S}}_{\varepsilon,2}(q, \lambda, T)|]^{(2i+1)} \exp[-\mathcal{S}(q, T; \sigma, l)]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.48})$$

$q(0)=\frac{y}{\sqrt{\hbar}}$

From (A.43)-(A.48) one obtain

$$|I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)| \leq \hbar^{\frac{1}{4}} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hbar^{2(i+1)}}{(2i+1)!} \hat{\phi}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) = \Theta_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar, n). \quad (\text{A.49})$$

Let us to choose an sequence $\{\hbar_m\}_{m=1}^{\infty}$ such that

- (i) $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \hbar_m = 0$ and
- (ii) $\lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ \Theta_\varepsilon^{(m)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2 = \lim_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hbar_m^{2(i+1)}}{(2i+1)!} \hat{\phi}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) \right\}^2 = 0.$

We note that from (ii) follows that: perturbative expansion

$$\int dx \left\{ \Theta_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2 = \hbar_m^{1/4} \int dx \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\hbar^{2(i+1)}}{(2i+1)!} \hat{\phi}_\varepsilon^{(i)}(x, T; \sigma, l, n) \right\}^2$$

vanishes in the limit $m, n \rightarrow \infty$. From (A.49) one obtain

$$\underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m) \right]^2 \leq \underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left\{ \Theta_\varepsilon(x, T; \sigma, l, \hbar_m, n) \right\}^2. \quad (\text{A.50})$$

Let us to choose now an subsequence $\{\hbar_{m_k}\}_{m_k=1}^{\infty}$ such that the limit:

$$\lim_{k,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k}) \right]^2 \text{ exist and } \lim_{k,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k}) \right]^2 =$$

$$\underline{\lim}_{m,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_m) \right]^2 \quad (\text{A.51})$$

From (A.51) and Proposition A.1 one obtain

$$\lim_{k,n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k}) \right]^2 = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k}) \right]^2 \right\}.$$

(A.52)

From (A.50), (A.51) and (A.52) one obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\lim}_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) \right]^2 \leq \\ & \leq \underline{\lim}_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \left\{ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k}) \right]^2 \right\} = \\ & = \underline{\lim}_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \int dx \left[I_{1,n}^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar_{m_k}) \right]^2 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Proof of the statements (3)-(6) is similarly to the proof of the statements (1)-(2).

Theorem A.1. Let $I_1(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) = I_1(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$, $I_2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) = I_2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$, where $I_1(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)$ is given via Eq.(A.22a)-Eq.(A.22b). Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_1^2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)] \leq \\ & \leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.53.a})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_2^2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon)] \leq \\ & \leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sin \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.53.b})$$

Here

$$\mathbf{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) = \mathbf{S}_{\varepsilon=0,1}(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) = \int_0^T L_{\varepsilon=0}(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t, \lambda) dt, \quad (\text{A.54})$$

$$L_{\varepsilon=0}(\dot{q}(t), q(t), t, \lambda) = \frac{m}{2} \dot{q}^2(t) - V_{\varepsilon=0,0}(q(t), t, \lambda). \quad (\text{A.55})$$

Proof. We remain that

$$I_1(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) = I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar) + I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar). \quad (\text{A.56})$$

From Eq.(A.56) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int dx [I_1^2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)] \leq \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)]^2 + \\ & \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)]^2 + 2 \int dx [|I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon) I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)|] = \\ & = \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)]^2 + \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)]^2 + \\ & + 2 \sqrt{\int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)]^2 \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)]^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.57})$$

Let us to choose now an sequences $\{\hbar_m\}_{m=1}^{\infty}$, $\{\varepsilon_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$, $\{\sigma_l\}_{l=1}^{\infty}$ such that:

$$(i) \quad \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \hbar_m = 0, \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon_k = 0, \quad \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_l = 0$$

$$(ii) \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 =$$

$$= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 = 0, \quad (\text{A.58})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{(iii)} \quad & \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 \leq \\
 & \leq \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2. \quad (\text{A.59})
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore from inequality(A.57),Eq.(A.58) and inequality(A.59)we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx [I_1^2(x, T; \sigma, l, \lambda, \varepsilon, \hbar)] \leq \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^2(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)] \leq \\
 & \leq \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 + \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 + \\
 & + 2 \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \sqrt{\int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 \int dx [I_1^{(2)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2} = \\
 & \lim_{l \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int dx [I_1^{(1)}(x, T; \sigma_l, l, \lambda, \varepsilon_k, \hbar_m)]^2 = \\
 & = \lim_{\hbar \rightarrow 0} \int dx \left\{ \int_{q(T)=x} D^+[q(t)] \Psi(q(0)) [|q_i(T)|]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cos \left[\frac{1}{\hbar} \mathcal{S}_1(\dot{q}, q, \lambda, T) \right] \right\}^2. \quad (\text{A.60})
 \end{aligned}$$

References

- [1] Vijay, R., Slichter, D. H. & Siddiqi, I. Observation of quantum jumps in a superconducting artificial atom. Phys. Rev. Lett. 106, 110502 (2011)
- [2] Peil, S. & Gabrielse, G. Observing the quantum limit of an electron cyclotron: QND measurements of quantum jumps between Fock states. Phys. Rev. Lett. 83, 1287–1290 (1999)
Nagourney, W., Sandberg, J. & Dehmelt, H. Shelved optical electron amplifier: observation of quantum jumps. Phys. Rev. Lett. 56, 2797–2799 (1986)
- [3] Sauter, T., Neuhauser, W., Blatt, R. & Toschek, P. E. Observation of quantum jumps. Phys. Rev. Lett. 57, 1696–1698 (1986)
- [4] Bergquist, J. C., Hulet, R. G., Itano, W. M. & Wineland, D. J. Observation of quantum jumps in a single atom. Phys. Rev. Lett. 57, 1699–1702 (1986)
- [5] N. Bohr, Philos. Mag. 26, 1, 1913.
- [6] R. Dum, P. Zoller, and H. Ritsch, Phys. Rev. A 45, 4879, 1992.
- [7] J. Dalibard, Y. Castin, and K. Mølmer, Phys. Rev. Lett. 68, 5801992.
- [8] Dariusz Gatarek, Continuous quantum jumps and infinite-dimensional stochastic equations, J. Math. Phys. 32 (8), August 1991
- [9] K. Molmer, Y. Castin, and J. Dalibard, J. Opt. Soc. Am. B 10, 524, 1993.
- [10] C. W. Gardiner, A. S. Parkins, and P. Zoller, Wave-function quantum stochastic differential equations and quantum-jump simulation methods, Phys. Rev. A 46, 4363 – Published 1 October 1992
- [11] Nicolas Vogt, Jan Jeske, and Jared H. Cole, Stochastic Bloch-Redfield theory: Quantum jumps in a solid-state environment, Phys. Rev. B 88, 174514 – Published 19 November 2013
- [12] J. E. Reiner, H. M. Wiseman, H. Mabuchi, Quantum jumps between dressed states: A proposed cavity-QED test using feedback, PHYSICAL REVIEW A 67, 042106 (2003)
- [13] D. J. Berkeland, D. A. Raymondson, and V. M. Tassin, Tests for non-randomness in quantum jumps. Phys. Rev. A 69, 052103 – Published 7 May 2004
- [14] H. M. Wiseman and G. J. Milburn, Phys. Rev. A 47, 1652, 1993.
- [15] H. M. Wiseman and G. E. Toombes, Phys. Rev. A 60, 2474, 1999.
- [16] M. Stojanovic, Regularization for heat kernel in nonlinear parabolic equations, TAIWANESE JOURNAL

International Journal of Recent advances in Physics (IJRAP) Vol.3, No.4, November 2014
OF MATHEMATICS Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 63-87, February 2008 This paper is available online at <http://www.tjm.nsysu.edu.tw/>

- [17] C. Garetto, Fundamental Solutions in the Colombeau Framework: Applications to Solvability and Regularity Theory, *Acta Appl Math* (2008) 102: 281–318. DOI 10.1007/s10440-008-9220-8
- [18] J. Foukzon, A. A. Potapov, S. A. Podosenov, Exact quasiclassical asymptotics beyond Maslov canonical operator. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1110.0098> Podosenov SA, Potapov AA, J. Foukzon., Menkova ER, 'Nonholonomic, fractal and related structures in the relativistic continuous media, electrodynamics, quantum mechanics and cosmology: Asymptotic methods in problems of classical and fractal pulse electrodynamics.' 2015 paperback. In press. ISBN 978-5-9710-1525-3
- [19] E. Nelson, Feynman integrals and the Schrödinger equation, *J. Math. Phys.* 5(1964), pp. 332--343.
- [20] V.P. Maslov, Complex Markov Chains and Continual Feynman Integral. Nauka Moscow 1976.
- [21] T. M. Apostol, *Mathematical Analysis*, Second edition, Addison Wesley, 1974.
- [22] W. W. L. Chen, *Fundamentals of Analysis*, Published by W. W. L. Chen via Internet, 2003.
- [23] S. L. Gupta and N. Rani, *Principles of Real Analysis*, Vikas Publishing House, New Delhi, 1998.
- [24] J. Lehmann, P. Reimann, and P. Hanggi, Surmounting Oscillating Barriers: Path-integral approach for Weak Noise, *Phys. Rev. E* 62, 6282 (2000)
- [25] M.V. Fedoryuk, "The method of steepest descent", Moscow (1977) (In Russian),
- [26] M.V. Fedoryuk, "Asymptotic Methods in Analysis", *Encyclopaedia of Mathematical Sciences*, Volume 13, 1989, pp 83-191.
- [27] Z. Shun and P. McCullagh, "Laplace Approximation of High Dimensional Integrals," *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* Vol. 57, No. 4 (1995), pp. 749-760
- [28] J. Foukzon, Strong Large Deviations Principles of Non-Freidlin-Wentzell Type - Optimal Control Problem with Imperfect Information - Jumps Phenomena in Financial Markets, *Communications in Applied Sciences*, Volume 2, Number 2, 2014, 230-363. ISSN 2201-7372